

The relative change in speed of light at the origin of gravity and universe expansion.

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Abstract

General relativity is an experimentally validated theory but it has never been reconciled with quantum physics because it describes the spacetime as curved. We demonstrate that we can describe the spacetime not as a curved spacetime by the matter or the energy, but as a flat spacetime where the relative change in speed of light due to the masses modifies the time and space coordinates. The speed of light then plays the same role as the mass in special relativity. We detail a number of results that can be obtained by the resulting coordinate transformation. Examples include: it linearises general relativity; the only invariant distances are those measured by an artefact, while those measured by the number of wavelengths depend on time, gravity and speed; the distance in number of wavelengths is the distance to calculate the interactions caused by the exchange of virtual particles; the energy of massive particles in a gravitational field is not constant; the current apparent expansion of the universe is due to the relative increase in speed of light due to the gravitational reorganisation of the matter; the black energy and the cosmological constant are zero; it is possible to measure locally the Hubble parameter by the change in light travel time over time.

Keywords: General relativity, Special relativity, Varying Speed light , Cosmological constant, Black energy, Big Bang

1 Introduction

The general and special relativities are the only two theories which modify the measurement of the time and space intervals. Paradoxically, they are based on fundamentally different principles: the invariant light speed for the first one and the spacetime curvature for the second one.

We will demonstrate that we can define a common principle to both relativities, on condition of modifying the invariant light speed postulate: it remains invariant in the observer's reference frame, but relatively to this reference frame, the speed of light can vary over time and space. Then, in general relativity, the speed of light plays the same role as the mass in special relativity.

The energy E of a massive particle depends on its

mass m and on the speed of light c according to the A. Einstein's formula: $E = m c^2$. If one of these two parameters changes when we observe it from another reference frame, the energy of the particle is modified. To keep these parameters invariant in the new reference frame, we must apply a coordinate transformation.

Special relativity covers the relative change of mass and the Lorentz transformation keeps the energy invariant in every inertial frame where the particle is at rest.

We will demonstrate that general relativity covers the relative change in speed of light. We will define a transformation denoted by S that keeps the energy invariant in every reference frame where the particle is at rest although the relative speed of light is different. The force needed to move from

one reference frame to another is the force of gravity. A direct measurement of the relative change in speed of light is impossible because every measurement is done in a local reference frame where the speed of light is invariant but indirect measurements are possible like changes in travel time, number of wavelengths or frequency .

This approach remains compatible with A. Einstein's equation of the RG:

$$R_{\mu\nu} - \frac{1}{2}g_{\mu\nu} R + \Lambda g_{\mu\nu} = \frac{8\pi G}{c^4}T_{\mu\nu} \quad (1.1)$$

The S transformation can generate all the metrics solution of this equation. On the other hand, the interpretation given is fundamentally different: the spacetime is flat, but the change in speed of light modifies the measurement of the time and space intervals and gives the appearance of a curvature. After having justified and defined the coordinate transformation for the relative change in speed of light, we will present results of this approach in three areas: the distance measurement, the gravity and the universe apparent expansion.

2 Relative change in speed of light

The principle of invariant light speed in the vacuum has been postulated in 1905 by A. Einstein [1]. In 1911 [2] A. Einstein assumed, "*nur in erster Näherung gültig*" : *valid only to a first approximation. If c_0 is the speed of light at the origin of the coordinates, the speed of light c at a location with the gravitation potential Φ is given by the relation:*

$$c = c_0 (1 + \Phi/c^2) \quad (2.1)$$

(Note: This formula does not take into account the spatial effect and underestimate by two the light deflection.)

Afterwards, he gave up the idea of varying speed of light in favour of general relativity.

In [3] [4] J. Magueijo reviews different varying speed of light theories in "the arenas of cosmology, quantum gravity and experiment/observation". He noticed "Even after the proposal of special relativity in 1905 many varying speed of light theories were considered, most notably by Einstein himself in 1911".

Even if none of these theories have reached a scientific consensus, it shows that the invariant light speed principle is still challenged.

2.1 Common principle between special and general relativities

Definition: a local reference frame is a reference frame where the massive particle is at rest and the time is measured at its position.

Invariant light speed in the local reference frame.

The second and the meter are defined by the BIPM [5] :

"*The second is equal to the duration of 9 192 631 770 periods of the radiation corresponding to the transition between the two hyperfine levels of the unperturbed ground state of the ^{133}Cs atom.*". Let $\nu_0 = 9\,192\,631\,770\text{ Hz}$ be this frequency.

"*One meter is the length of the path travelled by light (speed of light $c = 299\,792\,458\text{ m/s}$) in vacuum during a time interval with duration of $1/299\,792\,458$ of a second*"

Measuring a time or space interval consists in counting , in the reference frame where the radiation is emitted, the number of time periods T_0 or wavelengths λ_0 of this radiation:

$$\begin{aligned} T_0 &= 1/\nu_0 = 1.087310^{-10}\text{ s} \\ \lambda_0 &= cT_0 = 0.032612256\text{ m} \end{aligned} \quad (2.2)$$

We can define the speed of light as a length period (wavelength) by a time period: thus the speed of light is always one in every local reference frame.

If this radiation is emitted from a reference frame \mathcal{C}' , then, relatively to the reference frame \mathcal{C} , its frequency and/or its speed can be different. As observed from \mathcal{C} , the wavelengths and the time periods are different, the time and space intervals measurements are modified. If the speed of light in the \mathcal{C}' , observed from \mathcal{C} is invariant, it is special relativity, otherwise it is general relativity.

This principle of invariant light speed in every local reference frame despite its relative change from one reference frame to another, will allow us to define a coordinate transformation to move between reference frames.

Energy point of view.

In every inertial local reference frame, all the

physic laws remain invariant. It is true in particular for the energy $E = mc^2$ of a massive particle, its mass and the speed of light. But, observed from an other reference frame, they can vary. The transformation of the time and space intervals measurements allows these three parameters (E , m et c) to be kept invariant in every local reference frame.

Relative mass change.

The SR deals with the relative change of mass at constant speed of light. More precisely, when a particle goes from one local inertial reference frame \mathcal{C} to another \mathcal{C}' moving at a velocity v relatively to \mathcal{C} then,

- a force \mathbf{F} must be applied to the particle to accelerate it up to v .
- for the observer in \mathcal{C} the rest mass m and energy $E = mc^2$ of the particle increase by a factor $\gamma = 1/\sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2}$;
- we get the coordinates in \mathcal{C}' by the Lorentz transformation (the time and space intervals measurements are modified).
- thanks to the coordinate transformation, for the observer in \mathcal{C}' , the rest mass and the energy of the particle remain the same.

Relative change in the speed of light.

What would happen if the energy of the particle would be modified not by the relative change of mass but by the relative change in the speed of light? It means if we would move to another reference frame \mathcal{C}' , at rest relatively to \mathcal{C} , but where the speed of light would be different relatively to \mathcal{C} . Even if, for the observer in \mathcal{C} the speed of light and the energy of the particle have changed, in the new local reference frame \mathcal{C}' they would remain unchanged. This requires a coordinate transformation. The force needed to change the energy of the particle observed from \mathcal{C} is the force of gravity.

So, the two relativities allow, thanks to a coordinate transformation, to keep invariant the rest mass and the energy of a massive particle, and also the speed of light when moving from one local reference frame to another.

2.2 Coordinate transformation in one direction

Relativity of the speed of light .

Let \mathcal{C} and \mathcal{C}' be two local reference frames with zero relative speed (the general case of moving

frames will be addressed by cancelling the relative velocity by a Lorentz transformation). Let \mathbf{e}_i and \mathbf{e}'_i ($i = 0, 1, 2, 3$) be two orthonormal bases of \mathcal{C} and \mathcal{C}' respectively. The vectors \mathbf{e}_i and \mathbf{e}'_i are collinear and oriented in the same direction. x^i and x'^i denote the coordinates of an event in \mathbf{e} or \mathbf{e}' respectively.

The speed of a radiation emitted from \mathcal{C}' in the direction x^i is c in the basis \mathbf{e}'_i but is $a_i c$ in the basis \mathbf{e}_i (it means observed from \mathcal{C}) and vice versa the speed of a radiation emitted from \mathcal{C} in the direction x^i is c in the basis \mathbf{e}_i but is c/a_i in the basis \mathbf{e}'_i (it means observed from \mathcal{C}').

Transformation.

We assume that the speed of a radiation emitted from \mathcal{C}' is c in \mathbf{e}'_i et observed from \mathcal{C} is: $a_1 c$ in the direction \mathbf{e}_1 and c in the other directions. Let's define the matrix that transforms the intervals dx^i in dx'^i and vice versa.

Intervals dx^2 and dx^3 .

As the speed of light is invariant in the directions \mathbf{e}_2 et \mathbf{e}_3 and the relative velocity between the two reference frames is zero then:

$$\begin{aligned} dx^2 &= dx'^2 \\ dx^3 &= dx'^3 \end{aligned} \quad (2.3)$$

Intervals dx^0 et dx^1 .

We are looking for a linear relation between primed and non-primed intervals:

$$\begin{aligned} dx^0 &= \alpha_1 dx'^0 + \beta_1 dx'^1 \\ dx^1 &= \gamma_1 dx'^0 + \delta_1 dx'^1 \end{aligned} \quad (2.4)$$

We have the condition if $\frac{dx'^1}{dx'^0} = c$ then $\frac{dx^1}{dx^0} = a_1 c$ thus we can find α and β such as:

$$\begin{aligned} dx^0 &= \alpha dx'^0 \\ dx^1 &= \beta dx'^1 \end{aligned} \quad (2.5)$$

with

$$\frac{\beta}{\alpha} = a_1 \quad (2.6)$$

To show the relations between the primed and non-primed intervals, we have plotted on the figure 1 the position of a radiation emitted from \mathcal{C}' as a function of time in the two bases \mathbf{e}' and \mathbf{e} . The slope of the lines are c and $a_1 c$ in the bases \mathbf{e}' and \mathbf{e} respectively.

Fig. 1 Positions versus time of a radiation emitted from C' observed from C and C'

The light travels the space interval dx'^1 (basis e') in a time interval dx^0 (basis e):

$$dx'^1 = a_1 c dx^0 \quad (2.7)$$

Likewise, the light travels the space interval dx^1 (basis e) in a time interval dx'^0 (basis e'):

$$dx^1 = a_1 c dx'^0 \quad (2.8)$$

From 2.7 et 2.8 we get

$$dx'^0 dx'^1 = dx^0 dx^1 \quad (2.9)$$

2.5 et 2.9 give

$$\alpha \beta = 1 \quad (2.10)$$

We choose a positive α so that dx'^i and dx^i have the same sign. Using 2.6, α and β are given by

$$\alpha = 1/\sqrt{a_1} \quad (2.11)$$

$$\beta = \sqrt{a_1} \quad (2.12)$$

Hence the transformation is:

$$\begin{aligned} dx^0 &= dx'^0 / \sqrt{a_1} \\ dx^1 &= \sqrt{a_1} dx'^1 \\ dx^2 &= dx'^2 \\ dx^3 &= dx'^3 \end{aligned} \quad (2.13)$$

We can check the effect of this transformation on a monochromatic electromagnetic plane wave emitted from C' at the frequency ν_0 and propagation

speed c in the direction ox' . Its equation in the basis e' is given by:

$$\mathcal{A}'(x', t') = \mathcal{A}'_0 \cos \left(2\pi \nu_0 \left(t' - \frac{x'}{c} \right) \right) \quad (2.14)$$

We can get this equation in the basis e by the transformation $x' = x/\sqrt{a_1}$ and $t' = \sqrt{a_1} t$, ($a_1 > 0$):

$$\mathcal{A}'(x, t) = \mathcal{A}'_0 \cos \left(2\pi \sqrt{a_1} \nu_0 \left(t - \frac{x}{a_1 c} \right) \right) \quad (2.15)$$

This is indeed the equation of a monochromatic electromagnetic plane wave whose frequency and propagation speed are $\sqrt{a_1} \nu_0$ and $a_1 c$ respectively. To increase the speed of light by a factor a_1 , its wavelength is multiplied by $\sqrt{a_1}$ and its time period by $1/\sqrt{a_1}$.

2.3 Coordinate transformation in the four directions

We can obtain directly the transformation for the two other space directions. We choose for the directions e_2 et e_3 a speed ratio of a_2 et a_3 .

If the relative speed of light changes over time by a factor a_0 , the three spacial directions are modified in the same way:

$$\begin{cases} dx^0 = dx'^0 / \sqrt{a_0} \\ dx^1 = \sqrt{a_0} dx'^1 \\ dx^2 = \sqrt{a_0} dx'^2 \\ dx^3 = \sqrt{a_0} dx'^3 \end{cases} \quad (2.16)$$

Thus, we have defined 4 elementary transformations able to transform the intervals dx^μ in dx'^μ :

$$\frac{\partial x^\mu}{\partial x'^\nu} = S_0^{-1} = \begin{pmatrix} 1/\sqrt{a_0} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \sqrt{a_0} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \sqrt{a_0} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \sqrt{a_0} \end{pmatrix}$$

$$\frac{\partial x^\mu}{\partial x'^\nu} = S_1^{-1} = \begin{pmatrix} 1/\sqrt{a_1} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \sqrt{a_1} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}$$

$$\frac{\partial x^\mu}{\partial x'^\nu} = S_2^{-1} = \begin{pmatrix} 1/\sqrt{a_2} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \sqrt{a_2} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}$$

$$\frac{\partial x^\mu}{\partial x'^\nu} = S_3^{-1} = \begin{pmatrix} 1/\sqrt{a_3} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \sqrt{a_3} \end{pmatrix}$$

The general transformation S^{-1} is the product of these four transformations:

$$S = \frac{\partial x'^\mu}{\partial x^\nu} = S_0 S_1 S_2 S_3 = \begin{pmatrix} \sqrt{a_0 a_1 a_2 a_3} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1/\sqrt{a_0 a_1} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1/\sqrt{a_0 a_2} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1/\sqrt{a_0 a_3} \end{pmatrix} \quad (2.17)$$

The S matrix is able to transform an interval dx^μ in dx'^μ when the relative speed of light changes in the four directions between two reference frames which relative speed is zero.

2.4 Einstein's equation solutions

All the metrics $g_{\mu\nu}$ which are solutions of the Einstein's equation 1.1 can be obtained by a S transformation. As $g_{\mu\nu}$ is a real symmetric matrix, it can be diagonalized. The metric in this basis can be expressed by the equation:

$$\begin{aligned} ds^2 &= g_{\mu\nu} dx^\mu dx^\nu \\ &= -b_0^2(dx^0)^2 + b_1^2(dx^1)^2 \\ &\quad + b_2^2(dx^2)^2 + b_3^2(dx^3)^2 \end{aligned} \quad (2.18)$$

We can also write a metric generated by the relative change in speed of light in the four directions of the spacetime:

$$\begin{aligned} ds^2 &= (S.ds)^t \cdot \eta \cdot S.ds \\ &= -a_0 a_1 a_2 a_3 (dx^0)^2 + \frac{(dx^1)^2}{a_0 a_1} \\ &\quad + \frac{(dx^2)^2}{a_0 a_2} + \frac{(dx^3)^2}{a_0 a_3} \end{aligned} \quad (2.19)$$

The coefficients of the equations 2.18 and 2.19 must be identical. If all the b_μ^2 are positive, then

$$\begin{aligned} b_0^2 &= a_0 a_1 a_2 a_3 & a_0 &= 1/\sqrt{b_0^2 b_1^2 b_2^2 b_3^2} \\ b_1^2 &= 1/(a_0 a_1) & a_1 &= \sqrt{b_0^2 b_2^2 b_3^2 / b_1^2} \\ b_2^2 &= 1/(a_0 a_2) & a_2 &= \sqrt{b_0^2 b_1^2 b_3^2 / b_2^2} \\ b_3^2 &= 1/(a_0 a_3) & a_3 &= \sqrt{b_0^2 b_1^2 b_2^2 / b_3^2} \end{aligned} \quad (2.20)$$

According to the Sylvester's law of inertia, the number of positive and negative eigenvalues is invariant by a change of basis, so it means that the metric 2.18 must always have one negative and three positive coefficients.

2.20 provides the solution for a negative time coefficient. If the negative coefficient is x^1 instead x^0 then a_1 becomes $-\sqrt{b_0^2 b_2^2 b_3^2 / b_1^2}$, the others being unchanged. And so on... Therefore, every metric which is a solution of the Einstein's equation can be obtained by the product of the four elementary S_μ transformations.

2.5 Forces of gravity due to the change in speed of light

The change in speed of light in the three space directions can produce any force.

Notation: \mathbf{Q} is a four-vector, while Q^{x^i} and $Q^{t x^i}$ are the components of \mathbf{Q} in the bases \mathbf{e} et \mathbf{e}' respectively.

The general metric got by the S transformation is 2.19. We choose $a_0 = 1$

$$\begin{aligned} ds^2 &= g_{tt} c^2 dt^2 + g_{xx} dx^2 + g_{yy} dy^2 + g_{zz} dz^2 \\ &= -a_1 a_2 a_3 c^2 dt^2 + \frac{dx^2}{a_1} + \frac{dy^2}{a_2} + \frac{dz^2}{a_3} \end{aligned} \quad (2.21)$$

The four-acceleration of the particle is the covariant derivative of the four-speed. The particle is at rest, so the four-acceleration is zero:

$$\begin{aligned} 0 &= \frac{DU^i}{d\tau} \\ &= \frac{dU^i}{d\tau} + \Gamma_{\mu\nu}^i U^\mu U^\nu \\ &= \frac{d^2 x^i}{d\tau^2} + \Gamma_{\mu\nu}^i U^\mu U^\nu \end{aligned} \quad (2.22)$$

$m \frac{d^2 x^i}{d\tau^2}$ is the force of gravity denoted by F_g^i . The particle is at rest: $U_x = U_y = U_z = 0$. As $\mathbf{U} \cdot \mathbf{U} = -c^2$, $U^t = c$ and $U^t = c/\sqrt{-g_{tt}}$. By simplifying 2.22:

$$F_g^i = \frac{mc^2}{g_{tt}} \Gamma_{tt}^i \quad (2.23)$$

The Christoffel symbols can be obtained by the formula:

$$\Gamma_{\mu\nu}^i = \frac{1}{2} g^{i\alpha} (\partial_\mu g_{\nu\alpha} + \partial_\nu g_{\alpha\mu} - \partial_\alpha g_{\mu\nu}) \quad (2.24)$$

In order to calculate Γ_{tt}^i , we have $\mu = \nu = t$. We assume $\frac{da_i}{dx^j} = 0$ si $i \neq j$. As $g_{tt} = -a_1 a_2 a_3$, $g^{xx} = a_1$, $g^{yy} = a_2$, $g^{zz} = a_3$ and g is diagonal, by simplifying 2.24 one obtains:

$$\begin{aligned} \Gamma_{tt}^t &= 0 \\ \Gamma_{tt}^x &= -\frac{1}{2} g^{xx} \partial_x g_{tt} = \frac{1}{2} a_1 a_2 a_3 \frac{da_1}{dx} \\ \Gamma_{tt}^y &= -\frac{1}{2} g^{yy} \partial_y g_{tt} = \frac{1}{2} a_1 a_2 a_3 \frac{da_2}{dy} \\ \Gamma_{tt}^z &= -\frac{1}{2} g^{zz} \partial_z g_{tt} = \frac{1}{2} a_1 a_2 a_3 \frac{da_3}{dz} \end{aligned} \quad (2.25)$$

Using 2.23, we finally obtain

$$F_g^i = -\frac{m c^2}{2} \left(0, \frac{da_1}{dx}, \frac{da_2}{dy}, \frac{da_3}{dz} \right) \quad (2.26)$$

We can see that the force in one direction is proportional to the change in speed of light in this direction.

2.6 Massive particle energy

The formula 2.19 shows that the proper time of a massive particle at rest is:

$$d\tau = dt' = \sqrt{a_0 a_1 a_2 a_3} dt$$

and then, the relation between the frequencies ν et ν' in the bases \mathbf{e} and \mathbf{e}' are:

$$\nu = \sqrt{a_0 a_1 a_2 a_3} \nu'$$

A massive particle at rest that decays into a photon in \mathcal{C}' has an energy $E' = h \nu' = m c^2$. The frequency of this photon in the basis \mathbf{e} is $\nu = \sqrt{a_0 a_1 a_2 a_3} \nu'$. But its energy in \mathbf{e} is $E = h \nu$ therefore

$$\boxed{E = \sqrt{a_0 a_1 a_2 a_3} m c^2} \quad (2.27)$$

If the particle has also a momentum p' in \mathcal{C}' , its energy in \mathbf{e} is:

$$E^2 = a_0 a_1 a_2 a_3 (m^2 c^4 + p'^2 c^2) \quad (2.28)$$

3 Distances measurement

3.1 Procedure and notation

The distances between the two ends of an artefact (material object) can be measured in three different ways:

Artefact : we measure the distance with a calibrated artefact. This material distance is denoted by D .

Travel time : we measure D by the travel time of light. We convert this time interval in a space interval by multiplying by $c = 299\,792\,458$ m/s. We denote this time distance by D_t .

Number of wavelengths : We count the number of wavelengths needed to cover D . We multiply it by the wavelength in meter and we denote it D_{is} as representing the interaction distance D_{is} .

We perform the three measurements in the first reference frame \mathcal{C} (basis \mathbf{e}) and the meter is defined so that the three results are the same: $D = D_t = D_{is}$. Then, we move the artefact and the measuring instruments in another reference frame \mathcal{C}' (basis \mathbf{e}'). We perform again the same measurements we denote D' , D'_t et D'_{is} . Then, we compare the primed and non-primed results.

3.2 Distance measurement in general relativity

We assume that the relative velocity between the two reference frames \mathcal{C} and \mathcal{C}' is zero and the speed of a radiation emitted from \mathcal{C}' is ac in the basis \mathbf{e} .

Material distance. The ratio between the two ends of the measured artefact and the calibrated one has no dimension and thus it does not depend on the reference frame: $D' = D$.

Travel time. A radiation emitted from \mathcal{C} needs a time $t_1 = D/c$ to cover D .

The speed of a radiation emitted from \mathcal{C}' is ac in the base \mathbf{e} , thus its travel time to cover D is $t_2 = D/(ac)$ in the base \mathbf{e} and $t'_2 = \sqrt{a} t_2 = D/(\sqrt{a}c)$ in the base \mathbf{e}' . The relation between the travel time t' et t in \mathcal{C}' and \mathcal{C} is:

$$\boxed{t' = t/\sqrt{a}} \quad (3.1)$$

The time distance in \mathcal{C}' is:

$$\boxed{D'_t = D/\sqrt{a}} \quad (3.2)$$

The time distance depends on the reference frame and is longer when the relative speed of light is slower.

Number of wavelengths. To compare the wavelengths, we must express them in the same basis. Let O_1 and O_2 be two ν_0 frequency monochromatic electromagnetic plane waves emitted from \mathcal{C} and \mathcal{C}' respectively. O_1 wavelength in \mathbf{e} is $\lambda_1 = c/\nu_0$ and O_2 wavelength in \mathbf{e}' is $\lambda'_2 = c/\nu_0$. According to 2.15, O_2 wavelength in \mathbf{e} is $\lambda_2 = a c/(\sqrt{a} \nu_0) = \sqrt{a} \lambda_1$. In \mathbf{e} , O_1 needs $N = D/\lambda_1$ wavelengths to cover D while O_2 needs $N' = D/(\sqrt{a} \lambda_1)$. Thus

$$N' = N/\sqrt{a} \quad (3.3)$$

$$\boxed{D'_{is} = D/\sqrt{a}} \quad (3.4)$$

The number of wavelengths decreases when the speed of light increases.

In general relativity we have:

- a material distance that defines the unit of length independently of the reference frame.
- a time distance proportional to $1/\sqrt{a}$. It defines a travel time.
- a distance measured in number of wavelengths which, in RG, is equal to the time distance. We call it interaction distance because it defines the distance for the interactions caused by the exchange of virtual particles. We exclude the gravitation because the mechanism explaining the relative change in speed of light is unknown. The change in speed of light modifies the time distance and the interaction distance without changing the material distance.

The difference between these three methodologies depends on the gravitational field and its direction 4.10, 4.11 and on the time 5.12. On the scales accessible to us, the difference remains minimal and is difficult to measure. It would become considerable near a black hole or compared to the early universe.

Numerical example

A one meter artefact has been calibrated at the surface of the Earth on an horizontal position by

the methodology defined by the BIPM. Let N_\perp and N_\parallel the number of wavelengths needed to cover the distance of the artefact vertically and horizontally respectively. According to (3.3, 4.10 and 4.11), we have:

$$N_\perp = N_\parallel \sqrt{\frac{c_\parallel}{c_\perp}} \approx 1 + \frac{GM}{2rc^2} \quad (3.5)$$

The mass of the Earth is $M = 5.9710^{24}kg$ and its radius is $r = 6360 km$). When measured vertically, its time and interaction distances will be $\simeq 0.35 nm$ longer compared to the horizontal measurement.

3.3 Distance measurement in special relativity

The inertial reference frame \mathcal{C}' has been accelerated and move at a constant speed v in the direction ox relatively to \mathcal{C} . $\gamma = 1/\sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2}$ is the Lorentz factor.

Let's compare the measurements results in \mathcal{C} et \mathcal{C}' .

Material distance. For the same reason as in §3.2, the material distance does not depend on the reference frame: $D' = D$.

Travel time. As the speed of light is the same in \mathcal{C} and \mathcal{C}' , the time needed to cover the distance D is the same in \mathcal{C} and \mathcal{C}' : $D'_t = D_t = D$.

Number of wavelengths. The coordinates in \mathcal{C} and \mathcal{C}' are related by the Lorentz transformation. We can write it as the product of two transformations:

$$\begin{aligned} \Lambda &= \Lambda_t \cdot \Lambda_D \\ &= \begin{pmatrix} \gamma & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \gamma & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \gamma & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \gamma \end{pmatrix} \cdot \begin{pmatrix} 1 & -\beta & 0 & 0 \\ -\beta & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1/\gamma & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1/\gamma \end{pmatrix} \quad (3.6) \end{aligned}$$

Let $\tilde{\mathbf{e}}$ be a basis at rest in \mathcal{C}' , collinear with \mathbf{e}' , where the clock ticks at the same speed as in \mathbf{e} . We denote the intervals by:

$$ds_{\tilde{\mathbf{e}}} = \begin{pmatrix} c d\tilde{t} \\ d\tilde{x} \\ d\tilde{y} \\ d\tilde{z} \end{pmatrix}, ds_{\mathbf{e}} = \begin{pmatrix} c dt \\ dx \\ dy \\ dz \end{pmatrix} \text{ and } ds_{\mathbf{e}'} = \begin{pmatrix} c dt' \\ dx' \\ dy' \\ dz' \end{pmatrix}$$

We have:

$$ds_{\mathbf{e}'} = \Lambda_t \cdot ds_{\tilde{\mathbf{e}}}, ds_{\tilde{\mathbf{e}}} = \Lambda_D \cdot ds_{\mathbf{e}}$$

Λ_t expands the time intervals and keeps invariant the speed of light.

Λ_D changes the frequency and/or the direction of the radiation but keeps the proper time and the speed of light invariant.

O_1 and O_2 are two monochromatic electromagnetic plane waves emitted from \mathcal{C} and \mathcal{C}' at the frequency ν_0 in their local reference frame. O_1 wavelength in \mathbf{e} is $\lambda_1 = c/\nu_0 = \lambda_0$ and O_2 wavelength in \mathbf{e}' is $\lambda'_2 = c/\nu_0 = \lambda_0$. As $\tilde{\mathbf{e}}$ and \mathbf{e} have the same proper time and the same speed of light, the distances covered at the same speed and during the same time interval are identical. O_2 frequency in $\tilde{\mathbf{e}}$ is $\tilde{\nu}_0 = \nu_0/\gamma$ and its wavelength $\lambda_2 = \gamma\lambda'_2 = \gamma\lambda_0$. Thus, O_2 travels a material distance $\gamma\lambda_0$ per time period. O_1 needs $N = D/\lambda_0$ wavelength to cover D in \mathcal{C} and O_2 needs $N' = D/\gamma\lambda_0$ wavelengths to cover D in \mathcal{C}' :

$$N' = N/\gamma \quad (3.7)$$

and thus, regardless of the direction:

$$\boxed{D'_{is} = \frac{D}{\gamma}} \quad (3.8)$$

In special relativity, two different distances must be defined:

- a material distance that defines the unit of length regardless of the reference frame.
- an interaction distance which is proportional to $1/\gamma$. When the speed increases, for a given material distance, the particles are closer from the point of view of the interactions. It should be noted that the Lorentz transformation is based on the interaction distance, thus the length contraction affects only the interaction distance and not the material distance.

Note: by combining 3.4 and 3.8 we obtain:

$$\boxed{D'_{is} = \frac{D}{\sqrt{a}\gamma}} \quad (3.9)$$

Numerical example

This effect is difficult to measure on Earth because the gravity effects prevail. For example, a speed

of 10km/s increases the wavelengths by a factor $\gamma = 1 + 0.55 \cdot 10^{-9}$.

The highest energy cosmic ray ever observed had an energy of 50 J . If it was a proton, the wavelengths would be increased by a factor $\gamma \simeq 3 \cdot 10^{11}$.

4 Schwarzschild metric

We consider a spherically symmetric system with a central mass M ; three reference frames \mathcal{C} , \mathcal{C}' and \mathcal{C}'' , each having a coordinates basis \mathbf{e} , \mathbf{e}' , \mathbf{e}'' , the subscript c or s denotes Cartesian or spherical coordinates; a massive particle in free fall (mass m); \mathcal{C}'' is the inertial reference frame of the particle. \mathcal{C}' is the reference frame motionless relative to M and \mathcal{C} . \mathcal{C}' position is redefined at each moment to coincide with the particle; \mathcal{C} is the reference frame located at the infinity where the effects of M are negligible; the speed of the particle is zero in \mathcal{C}'' and v' in \mathcal{C}' .

4.1 Derivation

Let us define the coordinate transformation from \mathcal{C}'' to \mathcal{C} .

Definition of the transformation.

In the Cartesian basis \mathbf{e}''_c , the displacement four-vector is:

$$ds = ds_{\mathbf{e}''_c} = \begin{pmatrix} cdt'' \\ dx'' \\ dy'' \\ dz'' \end{pmatrix} \quad (4.1)$$

\mathcal{C}'' is an inertial reference frame, so its Minkowski metric is:

$$ds^2 = ds_{\mathbf{e}''_c}^t \eta ds_{\mathbf{e}''_c} \\ = -c^2 dt''^2 + dx''^2 + dy''^2 + dz''^2 \quad (4.2)$$

$$\text{with } \eta = \begin{pmatrix} -1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}$$

We can get the displacement ds in \mathbf{e}'_c by the Lorentz transformation Λ . We have $ds_{\mathbf{e}''_c} = \Lambda ds_{\mathbf{e}'_c}$. As the Minkowski metric is invariant by the Lorentz transformation:

$$ds^2 = ds_{\mathbf{e}'_c}^t \eta ds_{\mathbf{e}'_c} \\ = -c^2 dt'^2 + dx'^2 + dy'^2 + dz'^2 \quad (4.3)$$

We can transform the displacement from Cartesian to spherical by the Jacobian matrix $J: ds_{\mathbf{e}'_c} = J ds_{\mathbf{e}'_s}$ and then $ds_{\mathbf{e}''_c} = \Lambda J ds_{\mathbf{e}'_s}$:

$$ds^2 = -c^2 dt'^2 + dr'^2 + r^2 d\theta'^2 + r^2 \sin^2(\theta) d\phi'^2$$

Let us define the S matrix. The energy of the system is invariant over time: $a_0 = 1$. The system has a spherical symmetry, so the speed of light varies only in the radial direction $a_2 = a_3 = 1$ and depends only on the radius r . We denote $a = a_1(r)$ and the matrix S_r is

$$S_r = \begin{pmatrix} \sqrt{a} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1/\sqrt{a} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} \text{ with } ds_{\mathbf{e}'_s} = S_r ds_{\mathbf{e}_s}$$

We obtain

$$ds_{\mathbf{e}''_c} = \Lambda J S_r ds_{\mathbf{e}_s} \quad (4.4)$$

Thus the metric is:

$$\begin{aligned} ds^2 &= ds_{\mathbf{e}''_c}^t \eta ds_{\mathbf{e}''_c} \\ &= (\Lambda J S_r ds_{\mathbf{e}_s})^t \eta \Lambda J S_r ds_{\mathbf{e}_s} \\ &= -a c^2 dt^2 + 1/a dr^2 \\ &\quad + r^2 d\theta^2 + r^2 \sin^2(\theta) d\phi^2 \end{aligned} \quad (4.5)$$

a calculation.

We can calculate the force of gravity \mathbf{F}_g acting on the particle as in §2.5 from the metric 4.5.

The only non-zero component is the radial component and is equal to the gravitational force of Newton:

$$F_g^r = -\frac{mc^2}{2} \frac{da}{dr} = -\frac{GmM}{r^2} \quad (4.6)$$

Note: we can obtain the same result by using the conservation of energy: $dE + F_g^r dr' = 0$ with $E = \sqrt{a} m c^2$. We obtain: $F_g^r = -\frac{dE}{dr'} = -\sqrt{a} \frac{dE}{dr} = -\frac{mc^2}{2} \frac{da}{dr}$.

We can deduce:

$$\frac{da}{dr} = \frac{2GM}{r^2 c^2} \quad (4.7)$$

Integration with respect to r with $a(\infty) = 1$ gives:

$$a = 1 - \frac{2GM}{rc^2} \quad (4.8)$$

Using 4.8 and 4.5 we finally obtain the Schwarzschild metric:

$$\begin{aligned} ds^2 &= -\left(1 - \frac{2GM}{rc^2}\right) c^2 dt^2 + \left(1 - \frac{2GM}{rc^2}\right)^{-1} dr^2 \\ &\quad + r^2 d\theta^2 + r^2 \sin^2 \theta d\phi^2 \end{aligned} \quad (4.9)$$

Radial and tangential relative speeds of light

The coefficient a gives the radial speed of light c_{\perp} versus distance from the center of mass in the basis \mathbf{e}_s ($ds^2 = 0, d\theta = 0$ and $d\phi = 0$).

$$c_{\perp}/c = a = 1 - \frac{2GM}{rc^2} \quad (4.10)$$

The tangential speed of light c_{\parallel} in the basis \mathbf{e}_s is different because the space dimension is not modified ($ds^2 = 0$ et $dr = 0$)

$$c_{\parallel}/c = \sqrt{a} = \sqrt{1 - \frac{2GM}{rc^2}} \quad (4.11)$$

It is not possible to cross the Schwarzschild radius $\frac{2GM}{c^2}$ because there all the speeds are zero.

4.2 Energy calculation

We can calculate the energy of the mass m in \mathbf{e}_s as in § 2.6. The energy of the particle in \mathbf{e}'_s is $\gamma' m c^2$. Thus in \mathbf{e}_s it is: $E = a \gamma' m c^2$:

$$E = \sqrt{\frac{1 - \frac{2GM}{rc^2}}{1 - \frac{v'^2}{c^2}}} m c^2 \quad (4.12)$$

During a free fall, the energy is constant: the mass energy mc^2 becomes progressively kinetic energy. This formula gives the equivalence between the inertial mass and the gravitational mass.

We can calculate the energy E_g released when the altitude changes from the infinity to a radius R greater than the Schwarzschild radius $R_s =$

Fig. 2 Light deflection by a mass.

$2GM/c^2$, for a speed kept at zero ($\gamma = 1$):

$$\begin{aligned}
 E_g &= \int_{\infty}^R F_g^r dr' \\
 &= \int_{\infty}^R -\frac{GmM}{r^2} \frac{dr}{\sqrt{1-Rs/r}} \\
 &= \left[-m c^2 \sqrt{1-Rs/r} \right]_{\infty}^R \\
 &= m c^2 (1 - \sqrt{1-Rs/R}) \\
 &= m c^2 - E
 \end{aligned} \tag{4.13}$$

The total energy is constant: $E + E_g = m c^2$. At the Schwarzschild radius, observed from \mathcal{C} , the energy of the particle E is zero and the released energy is $E_g = m c^2$.

4.3 Light deflection by refraction

We can calculate, as illustrated in figure 2, when $R \ll 2GM/c^2$, the light deflection by the change in the speed of light according to 4.10, (we may neglect the speed variation 4.11 in the direction of propagation). The refractive index of vacuum is denoted $n(r)$:

$$n(r) = c/c_{\perp} = \left(1 - \frac{2GM}{rc^2} \right)^{-1} \tag{4.14}$$

We can apply the Snell-Descartes law to an infinitesimal variation of the incidence angle θ and of n :

$$n \sin(\theta) = (n + dn) \sin(\theta + d\theta) \tag{4.15}$$

For a small deflection, we may approximate $\cos(d\theta) \simeq 1$ and $\sin(d\theta) \simeq d\theta$ and thus

$$\begin{aligned}
 \sin(\theta + d\theta) &= \sin(\theta) \cos(d\theta) + \sin(d\theta) \cos(\theta) \\
 &\simeq \sin(\theta) + d\theta \cos(\theta)
 \end{aligned}$$

with 4.15, we obtain

$$d\theta = -dn/n \tan \theta \tag{4.16}$$

By differentiating 4.14 with respect to r and expressing $\tan \theta$ with respect to r , we have

$$\begin{aligned}
 \frac{dn}{dr} &= -\frac{2GM}{r^2 c^2 (1 - \frac{2GM}{rc^2})^2} \\
 \tan \theta &= \frac{R}{\sqrt{r^2 - R^2}}
 \end{aligned}$$

We can rewrite 4.16

$$\begin{aligned}
 d\theta &= \frac{2GM}{r^2 c^2 (1 - \frac{2GM}{rc^2})} \frac{R}{\sqrt{r^2 - R^2}} dr \\
 &\simeq \frac{2GM}{r^2 c^2} \frac{R}{\sqrt{r^2 - R^2}} dr
 \end{aligned}$$

by integrating we can obtain the deflection of the light α :

$$\begin{aligned}
 \alpha &= 2 \int_R^{\infty} \frac{2GM}{r^2 c^2} \frac{R}{\sqrt{r^2 - R^2}} dr \\
 &= 2 \left[\frac{2GM \sqrt{r^2 - R^2}}{rc^2 R} \right]_R^{\infty} \simeq \frac{4GM}{Rc^2}
 \end{aligned}$$

This result, obtained by the laws of the geometrical optics is the same as the one obtained by Schwarzschild metric [6].

5 Cosmology

Homogeneous universe

Friedmann-Lemaître equations, that govern the cosmic expansion, come from a simplified model of the universe based on the following approximation: as the universe on a large scale (a few billion of light years) is homogeneous and isotropic, we can model its expansion by only two parameters: its average energy density and pressure. Thus, we obtain only one stress-energy tensor $T_{\mu\nu}$ of the Einstein's equation 1.1 for the whole universe at every points and every scales.

But the gravity is not due to the spacetime curvature, but to the relative change in the speed of light. To have a gravitational effect, the mass density must be heterogeneous.

Let us define the S matrix for a homogeneous and isotropic universe. No gravitational effect can

occur in such an universe, thus $S_1 = S_2 = S_3 = 1$. According to 2.27, we must have $S_0 = 1$ to keep the energy constant. Thus the solution of the Einstein's equation 1.1 is $S = 1$ which is the metric of Minkowski. The stress-energy tensor is zero as well as the cosmological constant.

From a gravitational standpoint, a homogeneous and isotropic universe is an empty space, flat and static.

Heterogeneous universe

Even if the universe is homogeneous on a large scale, it is heterogeneous by the very nature of the matter. The average matter density in the universe is estimated to about 0.25 proton per m^3 . If this matter was evenly distributed at the early stages of the universe, it would be homogeneous on a scale of the few hundred of meters (we consider the material distance). Since, the gravity has reorganised the matter in structures like stars, galaxies ... Currently the heterogeneity has been multiplied by about 10^{22} . It has released a tremendous amount of energy which is likely at the origin of the apparent expansion of the universe.

Universe apparent expansion

To explain the current apparent expansion of the universe seen from the Earth, there is no need for an increase of material distances (Big Bang), but only a speed of light increase. This increase is caused by the energy increase ($E = \sqrt{am}c^2$). The baryogenesis itself needed a much bigger speed of light than it is now. An infinite value (meaning interaction distances are zero) would be needed to ensure a entirely homogeneous and isotropic universe.

Thus the speed of light is not a monotonic function of time, and the cosmological processes lasted likely much more than the 13.8 billions of years calculated based on a constant Hubble parameter.

5.1 Local metric of the universe expansion (CMB)

We can not define a global metric of the universe but we can define a local one.

Let us consider two reference frames: \mathcal{C}' is in the future or in the past and \mathcal{C} in the present at $t = 0$ each having one basis \mathbf{e}' and \mathbf{e} respectively. The coordinates of a displacement four-vector \mathbf{ds} in \mathcal{C}' in the bases \mathbf{e}' and \mathbf{e} are (dt', dx', dy', dz') and (dt, dx, dy, dz) respectively. As the apparent space intervals are bigger in the future reference frame

\mathcal{C}' , the time period is smaller. We can express that by a S_0 transformation where $a(t)$ is an increasing function of time with $a(0) = 1$

$$ds'_e = S_0 ds_e = \begin{pmatrix} dt' \\ dx' \\ dy' \\ dz' \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} dt/\sqrt{a(t)} \\ \sqrt{a(t)}dx \\ \sqrt{a(t)}dy \\ \sqrt{a(t)}dz \end{pmatrix} \quad (5.1)$$

The speed of light \mathcal{C}' at t , observed from \mathcal{C} is $c(t) = \frac{dx}{dt} = \frac{dx'}{dt'}/a(t)$:

$$\boxed{c(t) = c/a(t)} \quad (5.2)$$

The metric in \mathcal{C}' basis \mathbf{e}' is:

$$ds^2 = -c^2 dt'^2 + dx'^2 + dy'^2 + dz'^2$$

By applying 5.1 we obtain:

$$\boxed{ds^2 = -\frac{c^2}{a(t)} dt^2 + a(t) (dx^2 + dy^2 + dz^2)} \quad (5.3)$$

All the radiations observed from the Earth appear redshifted because our clock ticks faster.

We can notice that the metric 5.7 is not consistent: the frequency emitted from a point and reflected to come back must be kept unchanged (the proper time does not change). It means, the frequency decreases in the outward travel and increases in the return travel meaning that the frequency coming from a distant star (return travel) should increase.

5.2 Cosmic microwave background

The relation between the observed frequency ν of a radiation and its emitted frequency ν' is:

$$\nu = \sqrt{a(t)} \nu' \text{ with } t < 0 \text{ and } a(t) < 1 \quad (5.4)$$

It is estimated that the relic radiation was emitted when the temperature of the universe was $T' = 3000 \text{ K}$. Now its black body temperature is about $T = 3 \text{ K}$. According to Planck's law, the spectral

radiance of a body for frequency ν' at T' is:

$$B_\nu(\nu', T') = \frac{2 h \nu'^3}{c^2} \frac{1}{e^{\frac{h\nu'}{kT'}} - 1}$$

$$\implies B_\nu(\nu, T) = \frac{2 h \nu^3}{a(t)^{3/2} c^2} \frac{1}{e^{\frac{h\nu}{k\sqrt{a(t)}T'} - 1}} \quad (5.5)$$

where k is the Boltzmann constant and h is the Planck constant.

The current temperature of the relic radiation is:

$$\boxed{T = T' \sqrt{a(t)}} \quad (5.6)$$

The speed of light has been multiplied by about one million $(T'/T)^2$ since the emission of the CMB.

5.3 Relation between a and the Hubble parameter

The scale function $R(t)$ is defined for the metric:

$$ds^2 = -c^2 dt^2 + R^2(t) (dx^2 + dy^2 + dz^2) \quad (5.7)$$

The Hubble parameter H_0 is [7]:

$$H_0 = \frac{\dot{R}(t = t_0)}{R(t = t_0)} = \frac{\dot{R}_0}{R_0} \quad (5.8)$$

A radiation is emitted by a nearby star (reference frame \mathcal{C}') at the time t' and observed at t_0 ($t' < t_0$) where $t_0 - t' \ll t_0$. $R(t)$ can be approximated by the Taylor expansion: $R(t') = R_0 (1 + (t' - t_0) H_0)$. The relation between ν' and ν is [7]:

$$\frac{\nu'}{\nu} = \frac{R(t = t_0)}{R(t = t')} = \frac{1}{1 + (t' - t_0) H_0} \quad (5.9)$$

Using 5.4 and 5.9 we obtain:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{R_0}{R(t')} &= \frac{\sqrt{a(t=0)}}{\sqrt{a(t')}} \\ &= \frac{\sqrt{a_0}}{\sqrt{a_0(1 + (t' - t_0)\dot{a}_0/a_0)}} \\ &= \frac{1}{1 + (t' - t_0) H_0} \end{aligned} \quad (5.10)$$

By a Taylor expansion we obtain:

$$\dot{a}_0/a_0 = 2 H_0 \quad (5.11)$$

For small distances, $a(t') = a_0 + \dot{a}_0 (t' - t_0)$ thus:

$$\boxed{a(t') = a_0 (1 + 2(t' - t_0) H_0)} \quad (5.12)$$

As $H_0 \approx 70 \text{ km/s/Mpc} \approx 2.27 \cdot 10^{-18} \text{ /s}$, the speed of light increases by $\approx 4 \text{ m/s}$ per century.

5.4 Measurement of the relative speed of light versus time

As the speed of light is invariant in every local reference frame, its relative change must be measured in an indirect way:

Frequency change. When a radiation is emitted, its frequency decreases by $H_0 = 2.27 \cdot 10^{-18} \text{ /s}$ or $0.7 \cdot 10^{-10}$ by year when measured at the emission location.

Number of wavelengths change. We measure the number of wavelengths N to cover D at times t_0 and t . According to 3.3, we have

$$\begin{aligned} N(t) &= \sqrt{a(t)/a(t_0)} N(t_0) \\ &\simeq (1 - (t - t_0) H_0) N(t_0) \end{aligned} \quad (5.13)$$

Travel time change. We measure the travel times Δt at times t_0 and t . According to 3.1, we have:

$$\Delta t(t) \simeq \Delta t(t_0) (1 - (t - t_0) H_0) \quad (5.14)$$

The time distance of a material distance decreases by $\approx 7 \text{ nm}$ per meter and per century.

6 Conclusion

We have presented a consistent theory of gravitation and universe expansion that unifies the special and general relativities based on the common principle of energy conservation. The most significant results are:

The relative speed of light varies: even if it is invariant in the local reference frame, it can vary relatively to this reference frame. We have established the coordinate transformation to move from one reference frame to another one where the relative speed of light is different. This transformation linearises the general relativity.

The material, time and interaction distances are different. The material distance does not depend

on the reference frame while the interaction distance depends on the speed of light and on the speed of the particle. The time distance depends on the speed of light. These differences are measurable.

The force of gravity is caused by the decrease in the speed of light by the masses. The relative energy of a massive particle depends on the relative speed of light.

Even if the equation of the general relativity uses mathematics of curved spaces, the spacetime is flat. The apparent curvature comes from the change in speed of light and the needed coordinate transformation to ensure the energy conservation in the local reference frame.

As the material distances are invariant, the Big Bang did not occur: the current apparent universe expansion is due to the speed of light increase.

The gravitational effects are caused by heterogeneous mass and pressure distributions. So an equation of a pure homogeneous and isotropic universe cannot describe the universe evolution. As a result the black energy does not exist and the cosmological constant is zero. The universe evolution is governed by the heterogeneous distribution of masses and pressures.

The Hubble parameter can be measured on Earth by the time travel decrease of a material distance over time.

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